

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PAPE****FIRST NAME: STEPHANIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Word 2010 on Windows 10.

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

When starting a study program, it is essential first to get familiar with the university's standards and requirements concerning academic work and behavior. At Euclid University, every Ph.D. student has to work out and pass the introductory courses *ACA-401D International Academic Writing (Doctorate)* and *TPH-499 Argumentation and Critical Thinking* in the beginning before moving forward in his/her specific discipline.

In study period 1, the course instructors provide students with study material called *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* (EUCLID 2019). This paper gives an overview of the essential concepts of academic writing. Some of these concepts I want to discuss in this response paper.

2) THE ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

To obtain a certain quality level and to assure sound progress as well as mutual understanding in research activities, the scientific community needs standards. The study document comprises different, influential sources concerning the standardization of academic work. These standards include academic writing defined by some basic concepts. These are, among others, essay writing, plagiarism, reviewing the literature, using style guides, distinguishing American and British English, and Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2019, III–V). All these topics are related to each other. That means a writer of an academic essay must be aware of the plagiarism risk when

reviewing and citing literature. Furthermore, he/she should apply either an established writing style and use the English language as well as abbreviations/expressions coherently.

The purpose of an academic essay is convincingly presenting readers a research question and a suitable answer, also known as the thesis statement, embedded in an argument with sound reasoning and supporting evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1). These are the necessary components an academic essay should contain. To create an appropriate essay, one should pay attention to some relevant requirements.

First, the author must fix his/her ideas by asking a research question. He/she would do this as well as giving a preliminary response based on his/her current knowledge and experiences. The question's wording contains key terms that serve as guidance for the subsequent evidence search. Additionally, the meaning of the words tells the author what to look for in his evidence research.

Using an initial essay plan, the author can start the literature review. This part of the work is essential. Reading about the findings of other researchers broadens the author's knowledge of the topic and let him/her collect evidence to build up an argument and answer the research question. The aim is to provide readers with a balanced, mostly unbiased essay (EUCLID 2019, 2). Therefore, it is vital to include sources that not only support but also contradict the thesis statement. Taking notes while reading identified papers a second time helps to organize ideas and draft a matured essay plan.

Besides that, note-taking always requires source documentation. Electronic reference management systems are useful tools for the setup and maintenance of project-specific bibliographies and for citing purposes as well. Because reliable documentary listing avoids or at least minimizes the risk of plagiarism. Plagiarism means that "the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2019, 5). Just one example is false quoting or paraphrasing by citing the wrong or even worsen, none source. Plagiarism undoubtedly violates the academic code of honor (EUCLID 2019, 5). Such behavior rightly has corresponding consequences, such as the rejection of an academic paper. Thus, every author should cite the information sources correctly, not only to save face but also to acknowledge the achievements of other colleagues.

Citing comprises two parts (EUCLID 2019, 6). One is the in-text citation, which means that parentheses, naming the author(s) and publication year, or footnotes mark cited words within the text. These different kinds of in text-citation are also known as Author-Name style and Notes-Bibliography style. The other part is the bibliography or reference list (EUCLID 2019, 6, 10). Both are listings of the cited sources, usually placed at the end of any written document. Nowadays, one differentiates two common citation forms (EUCLID 2019, 6–9). Citing a source by using another author's unaltered words is called a quotation. A writer can quote brief information within the text. In this case, the use of quotation marks is mandatory. When quoting long text passages, the writer should place the sentences in a separate paragraph. That is also known as block citation. There is no need for citation marks, but the paragraph might have another style depending on the

specific style guide the writer must apply. The second citation form is paraphrasing. Paraphrasing means displaying another person's findings or knowledge by individual wording. When paraphrasing, the most important thing to keep in mind is to use their own words and expressions. Otherwise, the writer also risks an accusation of plagiarism. At this point, the use of a style guide might reduce such risk.

A style guide sets rules and standards in writing papers for different purposes and audiences of readers. Nearly every institution and publishing house have a specific style guide that writers have to follow. Some popular style guides are, for example, Harvard, Vancouver, APA, Chicago Manual of Style 17th edition with its sub-styles author-date, full-note and note, and Turabian (author-date). Turabian style is the one students should use when writing EUCLID response papers.

The Turabian style originates from a manual written by Kate L. Turabian in 1937 to guide students at Chicago University on the use of Chicago style in research papers (EUCLID 2019, 44). The application of a style guide ensures written documents with a continuous formal appearance of consistent quality. Stylistic specifications cover numerous issues that go far beyond grammatical topics and verbal expression (EUCLID 2019, 24–25). Especially for non-native English speakers, considering the differences between American and British English is crucial for a uniform, consistent writing style. Therefore, detailed spelling and terminology instructions (EUCLID 2019, 27–35) are incredibly beneficial. The same is true for further language skills like sentence length, voice, manuscript structure, formatting, and not at least standard Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56–61).

All the before-mentioned concepts relevant for writing papers are combined and summarized to so-called rules of thumb (EUCLID 2019, 14–16). These rules offer a practical checklist for students to consider the main aspects of academic writing. Their use is as helpful as taking into account the Eleven Important Reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17) that are about the significant basics of punctuation and grammar. Both pragmatic approaches should be the minimal requirements to check during the writing process to fulfill academic standards.

3) CONCLUSION

This summary paper is convenient because of its compact overview of the essential basic concepts of academic writing. Within a short time, the study of this document makes less experienced Ph.D. students familiar with the necessary information and useful advice about academic writing and further obligatory standards.

Besides, the sample of corrections to papers presented in Chapter 7 is helpful as a student struggling with his/her first response papers gets some ideas about the writing style which Euclid instructors expect.

However, regarding academic standards and the importance of form at Euclid University, I would like to propose an improvement for the current study document. In

my opinion, the heading of Chapter 8 is confusing because this chapter is actually about the Chicago Style. Nevertheless, the chapter's heading does not state that. Additionally, the formatting of this crib sheet is not comfortable for reading. I appreciate providing us with fellow students' notes. However, I would prefer a more suitable form for this document.

All in all, after studying this informative course material, I am optimistic about getting used to practicing academic writing in the required manner and quality soon.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University. (<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>). (accessed 03/09/2020).

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